

Navigating TechCentral's Ecosystem: Fintech in Sydney CBD

Report by coursework students of UTS 94663
Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and
Initiating Change, 2021 cohort

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TD School (ex Faculty of Transdisciplinary Innovation) is a new pan-university School at UTS, established in 2017 as a nexus for transdisciplinary thought and practice. The UTS TD School is on a mission to instigate a monumental, revolutionary change to tertiary education and research through transdisciplinary innovation. We believe the complex problems we're facing in the world require solutions that transdisciplinary thinking can provide. The first of its kind in Australia, our school brings together great minds from different disciplines to explore ideas that improve the way we live and work in the world.

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Team

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Foreword

This report is part of a series of student generated series about entrepreneurial ecosystems. Each report is a derivative of their coursework, conducted in collaboration with multiple industry partners and interviews with stakeholders in the ecosystem. The subject, 94663 Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Initiating Change, is a core subject in the Diploma in Innovation at TD School and a popular elective across other UTS degree programs. The subject was piloted as part of the launch for the Sydney School of Entrepreneurship in 2017¹ and draws directly on Martin's prior experience in visualising entrepreneurial ecosystems.²

The subject runs for three weeks in July, during which students are tasked with defining and exploring an entrepreneurial ecosystem, understanding its history and visualising its current state. Based on that knowledge, they then develop proposals that will bring the ecosystem forward.

The reports reflect the work that was presented publicly to invited guests and stakeholders in the subject, as well as members of the public who joined the presentations via the publicly available event page.

Methodology

The cohort of 50+ students was divided into random teams, each of which could choose their own ecosystem to focus on, with the only caveat being that it relates to TechCentral. Generally, the ecosystems were geographically in the immediate vicinity of TechCentral³, but varied significantly in terms of their sectoral focus.

Each team was instructed to consider the types of stakeholder based on Stam's seminal (2015) review of ecosystem factors. The general method of this study follows our own method of evaluating ecosystems that has evolved over years of experience, in consultation with an Australian wide network of ecosystem researchers. While our process is not yet well documented, it is entirely consistent with the 2018 guide produced by the German Society for International Collaboration,⁴ promoted by the Aspen Network of Development Entrepreneurs (ANDE). Teams adopt a qualitative approach, involving interviewing a broad range of participants to extract insights on their interpersonal connections and interrelations between factors and to identify specific opportunities for change. Each participant is believed to have a clear view of their immediate ecosystem, from which teams stitch together the more holistic view of how the ecosystem works.

The method can be tailored to specific ecosystems, ranging from rural communities through to internationally acclaimed innovation precincts. The breadth of Stam's framework and this method enables pushing back against the myth that innovation and entrepreneurship is primarily the domain of high-tech startups and VCs. While they do play a very important role, they are not the only organisations that matter to create economic growth (Brown & Mason, 2017; Spigel et al., 2020).

Field research for coursework follows the same principles as field research for academic purposes. As a result, the students' work mirrored the process of ecosystem research conducted by Martin Bliemel, for which he has ethics approval (HREC# ETH18-3020).

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¹ Bliemel, M., Schweitzer, J., Roy, G., Keitel, A., Nicolas, L., Miles, M., ... & Griffith, S. (2019, November). Herding cats to co-create cross-university courses in record time. *UIIN University-Industry Interaction Conference 2019*. University Industry Innovation Network.

² Bliemel, M. (2019). University-based entrepreneurial ecosystems and their visualisations. *University-Industry Innovation Magazine*.

³ <https://www.uts.edu.au/news/innovation/welcome-neighbourhood-tech-central>

⁴ <https://www.goethe.de/resources/files/pdf197/5.-guide-for-mapping-the-entrepreneurial-ecosystem.pdf>

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1 History of the Ecosystem

The innovation between financial products and information technology only became possible in 1866, when the first transatlantic telegraph cable was laid out, which drastically improved the communications between the Europe and North America (Woods, n.d.), and the discovery was also one of the most important ingredients in the modern-day internet. This was the commencement of the amalgamation between the two worlds, that formed the modern-day portmanteau word – “Fintech”, as short for Financial and Technology. In 1950, the first fintech product was introduced by The Diner’s Club – a single piece of cardboard card that served as a medium of payment to a restaurant in New York City, it became the first used of what is known now in the present day as a credit card (Diners Club International, n.d.). This prompted the pursuit of the entrepreneurial mindset to make the consumer’s life more convenient by creating more products in this space, which led to the creation of the first ATM (Automated Teller Machine) in 1967 for Barclays Bank in Enfield, North London. The ATM machine was one of the most impactful inventions and addition into the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem (EE) of the Fintech industry as it changed the way banking was done to the depositor by withdrawing/depositing their money without even going to the bank.

Although the banking system and the stock exchange was not new in Australia, it was only in 1987 when the infamous Australian Securities Exchange (ASX) was formed. Since its creation, it has been helping fintech entrepreneurs in the country of Australia and city of Sydney, inside its ecosystem, towards their fruitful ventures in going out in public (ASX, n.d.). In 1999, the world wide web shocked the world and paved its way into creating more of the mediums and enterprises that shaped the fintech EE in what it is now today. In the same year, a multinational bank – ING, entered Australia as its first fintech company and its oldest to date, offering banking services and many fintech products both in the past and in the present (Pash, 2018). ING later became more influential in the Fintech EE in Australia when they established their ING Labs to continue to create a better solution for consumers and influence others in the process (Spinale, 2021).

In 2003, Tyro payments entered the ecosystem and started out as a company specialising in merchant debit, credit, and EFTPOS acquisition, which up to date, maintained their exclusivity of their products as they offer it to the country (O’Brien, 2018). Additionally, Tyro had been an influential help in the Fintech entrepreneurial ecosystem by hosting their own Fintech Hubs called “Tyro Fintech Hub” in 2015 that caters the growth of the Fintech community in Australia, particularly starting out in hometown of Sydney CBD, which later expanded their operations to Melbourne (Tyro, 2019).

In 2015, in line with the establishment of Tyro Fintech Hub, an independent innovation fintech hub was also created called “Stone & Chalk” which was established solely to help fintech startups achieve their goals and further on grow into a fully formed company every step of the way. At present, they are prominent in the country that leads entrepreneurs to the right path not only for the fintech industry and community, but to other industries as well with the diversity of experts they have on hand (Stone & Chalk, n.d.)

The Australian Securities & Investments Commission had also contributed to the widespread development of fintech startups from 2016-present, when they first released the regulatory sandbox that exempts fintech businesses of certain licenses where it was previously a strict compliance given the complications and security measures in the financial industry. This regulation made their framework more flexible in the different types of innovation a fintech startup may create, subject to exemptions, that promotes the growth and development of the community in the country. (ASIC, 2016). This was the start of the fintech boom in Australia as reported by Angwin (2020) in the fifth issue of the EY FinTech Australia Census that shows the rapid growth of startups starting 2016.

In 2020, the COVID-19 had devastating effect not only in the country, but for the rest of the world. It affected many industries and had put into stop even the biggest companies in the country. However, it was the fintech industry that remained strong and true to their mission and goals and helped the country recover its unemployment rate by employing more Australians, through Fintech startups. In fact, the pandemic had changed the way these startups think, and managed to come up with more innovative and interesting ideas to help the community and country recover to its previous condition (Renando, 2020). It has resulted as well into many collaborations between the different companies and Government sectors in the country to help the community in need and in planning the different plans of the future for the possibilities that may come.

At present, FinTech Australia (n.d.) recognises the country with having over 800 fintech companies, and of the world’s most dynamic and exciting fintech industries. Having multiple internationally recognised organisations operating in the country. They also expected the same industry to grow from a \$250 million industry way back in 2015, into a multibillion-dollar industry by 2020 and present. Through the state-of-the-art technologies, infrastructures, and other resources Australia has, particularly in Sydney CBD, fintech entrepreneurs are ever more encouraged to pursue their passion in the industry and serve more people by making their life more convenient in every product that they innovate and discover upon. This is the reason why the fintech in Australia has been respected worldwide and is tightly knitted in the top ranked most influential fintech countries in the world, given its financial and

technology hubs located across the country, and throughout the different challenges it faced, especially in the times of the pandemic.

2 Ecosystem Map

In the visual map provided below, the Fintech Industry is used as the centre of the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem to find the stakeholders associated with it, then dividing these stakeholders by category. The map is analysed in terms of both primary and secondary stakeholders. In other words, the primary stakeholders of the map are those organisations or roles which are within the fintech industry, while the secondary stakeholders shown in the map below are those industry players outside but associated with the fintech industry.

This map visualises the stakeholders in the fintech industry and provides an understanding of the connections between stakeholders. It can be found that Sydney's financial and banking systems are relatively complete, but the technology sector is lacking in the fintech industry. The fintech industry is an emerging industry in the traditional financial service industry. Hence, this map also shows the strengths and weaknesses of Sydney's fintech industry. Therefore, if we want to strengthen the industry, we need to enhance the development of local technology and deepen the links with the financial sector to create a better fintech industry.

The map design features colorful arrows and easy-to-understand symbols that help readers identify the stakeholders, and roles in the ecosystem and provide a clear and understandable viewing experience. Each domain is associated with different actors, institutions, companies, technologies, and infrastructures. Figure 2 provides the reader with a detailed explanation, further explaining the meaning of the various icons and colored lines on the map. Dotted lines in green represent leading roles and dotted lines in red represent interactions. The blue dotted line in the figure represents regulation, with regulators such as APRA playing a regulatory role in Local Company and Incubator. It is used to ensure the fintech ecosystem's stability while balancing the aims of financial security, efficiency, and sustainability. Regulator, incubator, peak body, local company, investor, tech central, and banking system are connected by purple lines, representing the primary stakeholders of the whole ecosystem, these stakeholders play an irreplaceable role in the ecosystem. Education institutions, healthcare institutions, and media are secondary stakeholders in the ecosystem, they are connected by yellow lines.

Moreover, the finding of this map has limitations as follows. Due to the direction of finding stakeholders from the fintech industry in Sydney only, and finding connections from each category of stakeholders. Hence, it is not possible to make comparisons with other domestic regions, such as Melbourne, or international regions that might be leaders in the industry, such as Silicon Valley, USA. Also, the research for secondary stakeholders is subjective, and only a few representative organisations and companies in some relevant industries were identified.

- Local Company
- Peak Body
- Media
- Regulator
- Incubator
- Investor

- Accelerator
- Tech Central
- Hospital/ Healthcare institution
- Education Institution
- Banking System

3 Leverage Proposal

3.1 Big Why and What

The future ecosystem will enable the growth and sustainable development of fintech companies and organization. Some of the emerging technologies in the fintech ecosystem will include the following but not limited to Mobile, Biometrics, Open Banking APIs, Artificial Intelligence, RegTech, Blockchain and Big Data. These technologies make the fintech industry effective and efficient and will also lead to innovation in products and services in the industry. Furthermore, these technologies will be aligned along the consumer behaviour to maximize their applications and outcomes. Some of the key levers that need to be pushed for this development include actions such as adequate funding particularly at the seed level that is a particular challenge within the ecosystem as is. In order to further support the growth of the entrepreneurial ecosystem, greater transparency is necessary between ecosystem players in order to depict a clear picture of the resources available to them, including incentives, grants and funding at a federal, state and city level as well as the private sector. There would be a requirement for greater communication, transparency and collaboration between the different stakeholders such as the government, the private players, the users, the academic community and the wider population and community. Further levers include focus on high levels of research, development and innovation in the technologies by the private players, academic community and the government as well as the increasing level of education and awareness among the wider population by the academic community.

3.2 Who, How and When

3.2.1 Comprehension and Eligibility of start-up incentives and grants

The Challenge

Paul Smith, a critical observer of the Sydney Fintech EE as an AFR reporter, denotes the challenge of Startups in facing constant red tape. While financial systems go hand in hand with necessary red tape to ensure compliance and legitimacy is upheld the market, there still needs to be a "lot of work done locally

when it comes to understanding what incentives your start-up may be entitled to, and then getting approved for it.” This sentiment is echoed by the start-up community, layered by the complexity of application processes for grants and ultimately inhibiting access (KPMG, 2015).

The Opportunity (Levers)

To optimise the knowledge transfer and experience of past applicants, as well as offer a comprehensive list on all incentives and grants available to Sydney Fintech Start-ups, a centralised platform will be built. This platform will provide an overview of Grants and Incentives available and applicable to the Sydney Fintech Entrepreneurial Ecosystem. This extension to the broader EE is necessary given policies and incentives such as early-stage innovation company (ESIC) are applicable to multiple vendors within the system.

Not only will the platform allow for a centralised location whereby information on policy can be sourced (including key dates, eligibility criteria and external links), it will serve as a forum for support, enabled by a comments section below policy/incentive pages. By incentivising multiple ecosystem stakeholders to access this system through information relevant to multiple parties, it will accumulate broader and more diverse advice to address help sought by applicants which will be available through this comments section. This interactivity is intended to bridge the gap between those struggling to understand the eligibility criteria or are lost in the process, and those that are in a position to offer advice (either having been an applicant prior or having the knowledge).

To further combat the “complexity of application processes” experienced by start-ups in particular (KPMG, 2015), a quarterly session will be held on the most popular topics requested for help by the online community. Visitors to the policy pages will be able to ‘raise their hand’ by selecting the feature on the page to nominate the topic, which will be tackled in a quarterly seminar hosted by Fintech Australia and the relevant stakeholders to the matter.

Activators

1. Fintech Australia

As a peak body in the fintech EE and ‘Voice of the Australian Ecosystem’, fintech Australia is a vital activator given the body’s constant advocacy for growth through regulation in all levels of government on behalf of its members. Fintech Australia will be an essential voice for advice in the quarterly sessions, as a host to the discussion.

2. ASIC

ASIC is a regulator and is essential for the compilation of grants and incentives.

3. ASIC innovation Hub

The ASIC innovation Hub offers informal support to Australian FinTech’s in navigating the nation’s regulatory system. ASIC is intended to be a key source of support for the quarterly sessions and may be called upon if the communities most popular ‘hand raisers’ apply to the type of informal advice they offer.

4. City of Sydney

As a key local contributor to policy, the City of Sydney will be vital in their contribution to the composition of all policy and incentives offered by the local council.

3.2.2 Talent Acquisition

The Challenge

The rapid growth of the fintech EE has presented challenges regarding sourcing talent has the skills to uphold the level of complexity of systems necessary to support fintech technologies and systems (Bourlioufas, 2021). While policies have been established to encourage international talent targeted at the fintech sector, including the Global Talent Visa Program, COVID boarder closures pose a substantial barrier to such international talent acquisition (Simpkins, 2020).

The Opportunity

Instead, we propose that the fintech EE focuses on bridging the gaps between academia and startups to foster local talent and expedite research and development in particular. This proposal harnesses the unique location of AAIL, a leading AI research institute located at UTS, within close proximity to the new TechCentral. We propose that a placement program is built to allow PhD students to undertake a 6-12 month placement within fintech startups, incentivised by a 50% subsidy to the students fees on behalf of UTS. This model harnesses the unique expertise of local academia, while based off of a proven model exhibited in the UK whereby PhD students were granted 80,000 pounds p.a. for up to a 3 year

placement in startups (Smith, 2021). This initiative also address Right Click Capitals concern that “while tech central will bring together talented people, the key will be developing community and linkages between those who are around the area”

Activators

1. UTS

To subsidise the 50% reduction of PhD students fees, UTS as the academic institution will be required to step in to advocate for the program.

2. AAIL

The Australian Artificial Intelligence Institute is a world leading research institute in artificial intelligence, with a vision to develop theoretical foundations and advanced algorithms for AI, and to drive significant progress in related areas like computational intelligence (AAIL, 2021). The PhD program will be the source of academic partnering with TechCentral Startups

3. TechCentral Startups

Fintech Startups that reside within TechCentral will have the opportunity to be apart of the program, leveraging the research and development benefits to technologies relevant to their product offering.

3.3 Little Why

3.3.1 Value for the Sydney Fintech Ecosystem

It is clear that the pulling of these levers will facilitate great transition and growth for the Sydney Fintech Ecosystem. In the creation of a centralised grants and incentives platform, Sydney Fintechs will be able to collect all of the funding they are entitled to, and funnel it into their research and development programs, hence accelerating the creation of new and innovative technologies. This in turn will allow Sydney Fintech’s end products to be generated at a much faster pace, allowing the ecosystem as a whole to excel and thrive.

Further, through creating a link between institutions such as UTS through AAIL and Fintech Startups at Tech Central, the wealth of knowledge of both academics and start up professionals will be strengthened. This in turn will facilitate the next generation of Fintech professionals in Sydney, allowing up and coming students and graduates to make a real impact right from the start of their Fintech journey, in turn promoting growth of the ecosystem.

3.3.2 Value for Activators

Specifically, in the proposal for a Grants and Incentives platform, the activators of ASIC, City of Sydney and Fintech Australia can generate great value from this program. The NSW Government is heavily invested in the growth of the tech centre of Sydney (NSW Government, n.d.) of which the Fintech ecosystem is a part of. In pursuing active participation in this program, ASIC and the City of Sydney can immerse itself in the tech community and hence better develop strategies to help the organisations they will interact with.

Further, as a peak body of the Fintech ecosystem, Fintech Australia can generate value for itself in achieving their goal of “doing everything we can to grow our community and ecosystem” (Fintech Australia, n.d.). In hosting these quarterly events, Fintech Australia can further cement itself in the ecosystem as a peak body and accelerator for local Fintechs.

In terms of the AAIL students and Tech Central startups initiative, the Australian Government has the opportunity to overcome the challenge Australia currently faces in not having enough local talent and people with the right knowledge in the tech space. While Prime Minister Scott Morrison had incentivised overseas talent in 2019 by developing the Global Talent Scheme Program with three initiatives to provide visas to internationals in order to grow the tech environment in Australia (Department of Home Affairs, n.d.), COVID-19 disallowed these programs to be implemented and forced the tech community to look within. This education based initiative will hence generate value for the Australian Government in allowing follow through on its plan to accelerate talent levels.

Further, both institutions such as UTS and the startups they will partner with can both create value for themselves by sharing a wealth of knowledge between them and be the facilitator and receiver of a new generation of genius. In giving students real, high quality experience in the Fintech sector, startups will be able to benefit from job ready graduates. Further, UTS can benefit from increased students wishing to undertake this program as well as higher percentages of immediate job successful graduates.

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